

PEDAGOGICAL METHOD OF DISTANCE LEARNING USING MODERN INFORMATION COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8313871>

Abstract. The article describes the importance of providing education to learners through the most modern means of equipping educational institutions with information technologies in the process of distance learning.

Key words and concepts: distance education, multimedia, electronic, educational process, Internet, platform, Continuous education, educational material, textbook, computer, program.

Decree No. PF-6108 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 6, 2020 "On measures to develop the fields of education and science in the new development period of Uzbekistan".

The development of information and communication and new technologies in the educational system leads to the increase in the quality of education. The adoption of a number of laws and decisions adopted by our republic is important in equipping educational institutions with information technologies in the process of distance learning, and educating learners through the most modern means.

A new generation of electronic educational literature for improving the effectiveness of distance education; the use of multimedia e-learning manuals, e-textbooks, internet, platform HIMIS programs is important.

In the methods of creating electronic literature for the distance education system, it is possible to enrich the literature with experienced information, to create high-level electronic lesson processes that meet the requirements.

This distance learning is useful for professors, teachers, scientific and methodological staff of all types of educational institutions, and the creation of electronic educational literature for distance learning is useful for pedagogical personnel.

Creating electronic educational literature for the continuing education system. Electronic educational literature is designed to expand the imagination of learners, to develop and deepen initial knowledge, to provide additional information, and is created on subjects that are more in-depth. With the development of science and technology in the continuing education system, the need for the preparation of electronic educational literature on general professional and special subjects, whose content is rapidly changing, and taught in depth, is increasing. Elektron o'quv adabiyotlarining shakl va turlari:

- Electronic educational literature is a source that has the ability to collect, describe, update, store, present and control knowledge interactively based on modern information technologies;

- The electronic textbook is intended for the application of the educational method based on computer technology, for independent education and for the effective assimilation of educational materials and scientific information related to science:

- educational and scientific materials only in verbal (text) form;
- educational materials in verbal (text) and two-dimensional graphic form;
- multimedia (multimedia-multi-information) manuals, that is, information in the form of three-dimensional graphics in the form of sound, video, animation, and partially in verbal (text) form;
- tactile (felt, perceptible) characteristic, expressed in a form that allows the reader to enter the real world depicted by a stereo copy in the "screen world" and creates an imagination of movement in relation to the objects in it.

The data is created on the basis of the possibilities and tools of electronic information technologies, is structured in static and dynamic mode, is provided with sound and color images, contains a large amount of information and presents it in various forms (table, diagram, histogram, text, drawing, etc.), which can be used by learners during the educational process for independent work on themselves and control of their knowledge, which is constantly replenished, and which is intended for wide use, in the relevant authorized state organization a collection of data on the mentioned fields.

Electronic publication is magnetic (on magnetic tapes, disks). Optical (CD-ROM. CD-I. CDK. CD-R. CD-RW. DVD) can be provided on electronic media and on a computer network.

Electronic educational publication is an electronic publication with systematized educational materials corresponding to the field of scientific and practical knowledge, which ensures the creative and active acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities by students.

In the computer version, a word or group of words can be extracted from any program with a special instruction. Unlike traditional dictionaries, an electronic dictionary can contain a whole spectrum of media objects, including text and graphic images, as well as videos and animations, sound, music, etc.

Electronic methodological manual is a form of generalization and transfer of pedagogical experience, formation and distribution of new models of educational activity. In the electronic methodical guide, pedagogical experience is shown in the form of digitized videos of classes, student works created in electronic or converted form, planned for lessons.

The electronic study guide partially or fully covers the curriculum of the subject and includes an adaptation blog of information and is intended for distance learning and independent learning.

The electronic textbook is necessary for the learning of full-time students, and especially for independent work in forms of distance learning, because it:

- the studied material is different from the traditional paper printed educational literature: inductive approach makes it easier to understand due to conveying the material with years of exposure to auditory and emotional memories;
- trains according to the needs, level of preparation, and intellectual capabilities of students;
- frees from complex calculations and substitutions, providing an opportunity to consider a small number of examples that draw attention to the essence of science and solve more problems;
- provides ample opportunities for self-examination at all stages of learning;

- it allows you to hand over a file or papers to the teacher to make the work beautiful and clear;

- performs the role of a very tolerant teacher, providing unlimited explanations, countless repetitions, reminders.

The e-textbook is very convenient for practical classes held in classrooms, because it:

- solving a large number of problems using computer support, freeing up the time needed to analyze the solutions and their graphic interpretation;

- to conduct training in the form of independent work in front of the computer, leaving the role of leadership and consultant (consultant) to the teacher;

- allows the teacher to quickly and effectively control the knowledge of students with the help of a computer, specifying the content and levels of complexity of the verification activities.

The electronic textbook is very convenient for the teacher, because it:

- deliver materials that are small in size, but very important in terms of content, in lectures and practical sessions, independently of issues that can be studied outside the scope of classroom training allows them to deliver what they have left for them to deal with;

- frees from laborious tasks such as checking homework, various calculations and control work;

- allows to optimize the ratio of examples and tasks performed in the classroom and assigned at home;

- allows for individualization of work with students regarding homework and control activities.

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